

Nano-Au Particle Embedded Carbon Paste Electrode Sensing Platform for Electrochemical Detection of Temozolomide *in-vitro*

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Abstract

A versatile reusable electrochemical biosensor system is proposed by using carbon paste electrode (CPE) embedded with gold nanoparticles for the detection an important antineoplastic alkylating agent Temozolomide (TMZ)[1]. A finite layer of nanogold is formed with the homogeneous distribution of gold nanoparticles by potentiodynamic electrodeposition technique. The surface of the fabricated sensor has been characterized by X-ray diffraction and FTIR for the structural and chemical properties of the sensor system. The electrochemical efficiency of the present sensor system towards the detection of TMZ has been evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (ESI) and square wave voltammetry (SWV). Under optimized conditions, by applying SWV method, a linear calibration plot is achieved over the concentration range of 0.5 – 9 μM , and as low as 100 nM TMZ was determined in steady-state current-time analysis with the analysis time < 20 s.

Keywords: Electrochemical analysis, Antineoplastic agent, Nano-gold particles, Electrodeposition, Carbon paste electrodes.

References

1. Sun-Jin Kim et al, Clin Cancer Res; 21(20) October 15, 2015.